

Developing a Student Nurse Anesthetist Mentorship Program

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Background

- Student registered nurse anesthetist (SRNA) exposure to rigorous didactic and clinical education, and external stressors leads to chronic anxiety, stress, and low well-being
- Peer mentorship has been found to reduce stress, increase confidence for both the mentor and mentee, and allows mentors to gain leadership, teaching, and collaborative skills
- Little formal execution of or research on structured mentor programs for SRNAs in current literature

Purpose Statement

To provide recommendations for a lasting and impactful peer mentorship program at Kaiser Permanente School of Anesthesia (KPSA) that fosters collaboration and supports wellness among SRNAs

Methods

- Sample: Nurse anesthesia students that meet criteria between May - July 2023 ($n = 47$)
- Inclusion criteria: All current SRNAs in good standing at KPSA
- Exclusion criteria are all non-nurse anesthesia students, students not enrolled at this school of anesthesia, or those lost to attrition
- Surveys: Mentorship Evaluation Tool (MET), Perceived Stress Scale (PSS), and open ended questions covering overall program satisfaction, areas for improvement, specific requests, goals, and needs from a mentorship program
- Quantitative and qualitative analysis using SPSS and NVivo

Results

Open Response Questions: Thematic Analysis

99 coded instances belonging to 28 unique codes, with two emerging main themes:

- *Resilience Seeking*: Students want to turn to mentors for strategies, tools, guidance (*Milestone Guidance*) and psychosocial support (*Support of Well-being*)
- *Mentorship Formalization*: Dissatisfaction with inconsistent mentorship, want formal structure, mentor meetings, defined roles (*Structured Mentorship*) and opportunities to meet and socialize with mentors (*Mentor Engagement*)

MET, PSS, and Demographics: Statistical Analysis

- Spearman correlation showed a positive correlation between mean MET scores and employment ($r = 0.264$) and higher levels of parental education ($r = 0.130$)
- Spearman correlation showed negative correlation for PSS score and higher levels of employment ($r = -0.208$), and parental education ($r = -0.373$), and mean MET ($r = -0.328$)
- Linear regression analysis revealed statistical significance between PSS and parental education ($p = 0.044$) and mean MET ($p = 0.010$)

Discussion

- Higher mentorship satisfaction associated with lower stress level
- Moderate level of income may play a role in decreasing stress
- Potentially gender-based differences in stress
- Part-time employment associated with higher PSS
- Greater levels of mentorship satisfaction correlated with higher parental education
- Parental education inversely related to PSS
- Themes reveal belief that mentors can significantly aid students in navigating stressors and challenges
- Students identify benefits of mentorship
- Informal mentorship is significant barrier to building and maintaining a successful relationship with mentors

Strengths and Limitations

- Small sample size
- Stress levels are dynamic
- Predominantly female respondents
- Higher participation rate from class of 2024
- Researcher bias
- Validated survey instruments
- Free response questions provide rich data set
- Homogeneity between cohorts

Recommendations

- Integrate a formal peer-mentorship program into KPSA curriculum
- Incorporate structure including matching system, scheduled meetings, routine student surveying, and organization sponsored events
- Survey SRNAs in an interview format
- Incorporate wellness and financial coaching into the mentorship program

References

